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Principals Communication And Decision Making Skills For Effective Administration Of Principal In Public Secondary Schools In Abia State

Okeowhor, D. O., Orji, U. W., & Nwaelehia, P. C.

**Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study examined principals communication and decision making skills for effective administration of principal in public secondary schools in Abia State. Three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses guide the study. The study adopted the human capital theory by Becker (1964). The design of this study was a descriptive survey design. The population was all the 204 public secondary schools in the 17 Local Government Areas in Abia State. The researcher used simple random sampling technique to select 5 local government areas (3 urban and 2 rural), from which a sample size of 135 principals was selected. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled Principals Communication And Decision Making Skills For Effective Administration of Principal Questionnaire (CDMSEAPQ). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method at a reliability index (r) of 0.84. The findings of this study revealed that building synergy in the school system, creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals, creating mutual understanding in the school system, breaking down of information to the level of everyone to achieve target goals and carrying everyone along in the school system on ways communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objective in Abia State. Based on the findings of the research, the researcher concluded that communication skills and decision making skills help secondary schools principals in Abia State. Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made amongst others that principals should ensure that all forms of communication skills ranging from verbal to written to gestures and their likes be adopted and practiced in schools in for the achievement of objectives particularly when addressing teachers, students and all other educational stakeholders within the school.

Keywords: Communication, Principals, Decision making skills, School system

INTRODUCTION

Education remains a tool for building a united nation, establishment of traditions and cultural values for the younger generations which transcends from one generation to other generations. This is expressly done with the help of school administrators as channels to educate the young ones with the information they have acquired. No nation succeeds without her educational system therefore school administrators remain highly relevant in the drive to strong, reliable and resilient educational system. Principals are pilots in every formal organization especially the school. This is so because they have been found qualified and to have the capacity to run the secondary school based on the stated rules and regulations of the Ministry of Education as contained in the educational policy. The secondary school can be regarded as a workshop or field for skills exhibition for principals where high level administrative effectiveness is targeted at and thereby achieved with the right procedures and all sundry. Every school administrator strives to inspire his or her client, teachers and students to render

quality educational services to the school client. As a result of this, quality is of priority in this quest for qualitative staff performance in order to increase school administrator's effectiveness. The secondary school system requires the help of principals that are regularly kept abreast of changes in the profession. Principals' improve their skills and knowledge through high quality professional development programmes such as staff development. Staff development for principals can come in form of in service training which comprise of workshops, seminars, conferences, inter school visitation, participation in professional associations, independent study, staff meetings and so on.

Communication Skill for Effective Administration

Communication skill remains a veritable tool in the hands of principals for administrative effectiveness to be achieved. Communication however is a two traffic flow where information is sent across to someone requiring necessary actions to be taken. The action in tone sends a signal to the sender that communication had taken place. It becomes communication only and only if a feedback is gotten from the receiver to the sender. Communication therefore is an act of transmitting information in verbal or written form (Nwafor & Nwogu, 2014). The act in the definition described the method and /or means through which the information was passed across. The verbal nature of information may mean a lot and sometimes misunderstood because of the loads attached to the act. Communication may also be expressed in the form of body language where such means of communication existed in the school system. All information carries instruction/information and such instruction information is what the principals expected the subordinate to act upon. The other form of communication as contained in the definition above is the written aspect of communication. Written form of communication may look a lot easier because it is the visible form of communication. The only barrier to this aspect of communication is a situation where the sentence structure is beyond the level of the receiver. Where this is possible the information becomes incomprehensible for the receiver and as such feedback will not be received.

The heart of every formal functional organization is centered on the effectiveness of the communication skill of the principal. Communication is made up five different levels namely: Downward, Upward, Lateral, Diagonal and External.

1. **Downward flow of Communication:** this is communication that flows from higher level to a lower level in an organization, like communication from superiors to subordinates. This form of communication is used by management for the following purposes:
 - Providing feedback on workers' performance.
 - Giving job instructions
 - Communicating the organization's mission and vision to employees
 - Highlighting the areas of attention.
2. **Upward flow of Communication:** this applies to communication that flows to a higher level in an organization to those at the lower levels in the same organization. It provides feedback on how well the organization is functioning. The subordinates use mode of communication to convey their problems and performances to their superior. Upward communication leads to more committed and loyal workforce because the employees are given a chance to raise and speak dissatisfaction issues to the higher levels. This enables managers to accordingly take actions towards improving things.
3. **Lateral/Horizontal Communication:** this involves communication that takes place at same levels of hierarchy in an organization. It applies to communication between peers, managers at some levels. The flow of communication is not beyond those at the same level in the same organization.
4. **Diagonal Communication:** this is communication that takes place between a manager and employees of other workgroup.
5. **External Communication:** this is communication that takes place between a principal and external group such as education board, Ministry of education, suppliers, vendors, etc.

However, communication can take place in this format in an organization using these six formats:

1. **Memo:** Less formal than letter, more likely to be read, not confidential.
2. **Notice boards:** May never be read, good for staff to staff
3. **Letter to staff:** Private, personal
4. **Email:** Private, less formal than letter, less likely to be kept like letter.
5. **Faxes:** Personal, public

6. **Internal Newsletter:** Public, not for bad news, useful for minor but important news.

Other aspects of communication can be presented in a systematical order on a regular basis and to be as relevant, local, and timely as possible. The basis for this is because communication needed to be clear, easily understood and concise (Armstrong, 2012). In a further explanation by Armstrong, variety of communication methods existed and thus needed to be in spoken and written, direct and indirect. No organization survives when there is no proper communication flow. Communication is a way of expressing thoughts, ideas, feelings etc. Hence, all administrators need communication skill if effective must be achieved in the organization. In supporting the statement, Bennis and Nanus in Virginia (2008) emphasized that leadership is all about communicating and effective principals regularly utilize communication skills in soliciting beliefs and ideas, advocating positions, and persuading others. Virginia (2008) contributed that principals provide for systematic two-way communication with staff regarding the achievement standards and the improvement goals of the school; establish supports, and implements activities that communicate the value and meaning of learning to students; develop and uses communication channels with parents to set forth school objectives. Thus, communication emerged as a theme from the studies regarding the leader's role in providing focus on the vision and shaping the culture. Arlestig (2007:17) said, "Through communication, the principal leads and unifies his or her staff members in the work necessary for academic results and school improvement". In Arlestig's book titled principal's communication inside the school- a contribution to school improvement. He enumerated four important points that helped in achieving effectiveness in schools by principals. They are as follows;

Principals' Communication inside the School- a Contribution to school Improvement: this is about what goes on the school system between principals and teachers. The result from a study carried out showed that information dissemination were a daily affair with the principals even though they lack close contact with the principal. Major issues were on students' outcome and school improvement. The school was structured and cultured to accommodate, create a safe and sustainable atmosphere with less distraction and unexpected events.

Multidimensional Organizational Communication as a Vehicle for Successful School: this was structure on teachers and principals ideology on the use of information, affirmation/feedback and interpretation in different schools. The point was to strike a balance on principals and teachers reaction to information, affirmation/feedback and interpretation with regards to communication. The result for the survey carried out in sampled schools, information dissemination had upper credit although there was need to align with affirmation/feedback and interpretation.

Structural Prerequisites for Principals and Teachers Communication About Teaching and Learning Issues: this talked about other aspects of communication that make up an effective organization. Such aspects are issues of meetings and agenda. This is communication with a democratic leadership. This is a leadership that gives room for teachers to air their views on a particular matter as related to the organization. it is possible for the principal to take decision on every matter in the meeting but his or her leadership style accommodates suggestions and contributions from members of the organization for effective administration.

In-School Communication: Developing a Pedagogically Focused School Culture: this is a form of leadership style where principals treat suggestions from staff/ teachers with a sense of dignity with different experience and opinions. Where organizational structure and culture permits contributions from staff/teachers, the principals a two ways traffic trust is built between teachers and principals, and principals and teachers. By so doing, effective communication is built in the school system.

Sheffield (2006:15) described a recent study that scrutinized research on the effects of the principal's leadership on student achievement and identified 66 leadership practices in 21 areas of leadership responsibility. Two of the leadership responsibilities that had high correlation with student success were communication and visibility. For example, the responsibility of communication included being accessible to teachers, parents, and students; maintaining open lines of communication with staff; and providing means for the staff to communicate frequently with the principal. Why this occurred as discovered in the research by Sheffield is because most principals have delegated sensitive issue to their personal secretary especially vital information that requires immediate action. These secretaries in tune most times relax and disseminate these information when it is convenient for them and not when it required by the organization or school thereby making the office ineffective.

Communication defines organizational structure and culture. Its processes create and exchange messaging within the organization. It may involve some key components like network, interdependence, relationship, environment, uncertainty and messaging. Communication is a persuasive role rather than an individual skill (Kowlski, Petersen & Fusarelli, 2007). The communication structure and culture available in an organization determines how far or how much progress is available to the organization. A closed communication existed where information is disseminated to selected few. This is a form of hoarding and could cause total collapse to the system. An open communication system is such that information is not hoarded for any reason. Communication lines are tro and fro in the organization. This leads an effective organization.

Why Communication Skill is Necessary in the Organization

Apart from the fact that communication covers a wide range of issue in every organization, it is important to know why it has gone beyond important in every organization to being necessary. In as much communication in a definition was defined as the transfer of information from a sender to a receiver, with the information being understood by the receiver, it necessary to note the following: communication is essential for the internal functioning of enterprises because it integrates the managerial functions (Heinz, Mark & Harold, 2012). In manipulating the internal mechanics of the communication does the following;

1. to establish and disseminate the goals of enterprise/organization;
2. to develop plans for their achievement;
3. organize human and other resources in the most effective and efficient way;
4. to select, develop and appraise members of the organization;
5. to lead , direct, motivate and create a climate in which people want to contribute and;
6. to control performance.

Decision Making Skill for Effective Administration of Principals

Most organization failed especially the formal organization because they lack the capacity to take decision when necessary. Decision making is key in every organizational set up. Decision making by definition is the selection of a course of action from among alternatives; it is at the core of planning (Heinz, Mark & Harold, 2011). It is ascribed as one of the most important job available to managers and administrators considering to be the central job in every organization because managers are faced with what should be done, how ,where and when it should be done. Decision making is what differentiates a functional and effective administration from another. The role of decision making can never be overemphasized. Reason being that it channels the course of events in an organization. When decisions are not take when they are supposed to be taken, it results to deficiency on the path of the administrators. Most principals as well as administrators find it difficult to make decisions especially when it has to do a wide range of issues dealing with curriculum and its mode of instructions, negotiations and compromises, physical facilities, finance, pupils' administration, evaluation, supervision and public relations with both members within and outside the school environment connected to the school system. The challenges is that somewhat they have not acquired the knowledge on how certain issues affecting the school system should be handled and handled promptly.

Fatima (2012) posited that decision making process involves areas related to the students' wellbeing, teaching and non-teaching, Parent Teacher Associations and is concerned with the following responsibilities on the school principal;

- a. the principal must identify his staff members as a team working for the growth and development of the students;
- b. the principal must realize that as a team each member, staff and students have a large part to play in decisions that determine the school rules, regulations and programmes. School administration through staff meetings, student's representatives, clubs, committees and organizations should be involved in the running of the school through proper delegation of activities and responsibilities.
- c. the school principal must ensure that decisions and procedures in the school must be consistent with the underlying philosophy and mission of the school. This means that decisions should at all times aimed at achieving the set goal, objectives and interest of the school.

- d. the principal together with members of staff must always keep the ministry of education, school board and general public fully informed of the school policies, programmes, failures and successes. This means that the school as a place for teaching and learning, established by the community, must constantly take responsibility to communicate the affairs of the school to the people with a direct responsibility for it. Principal's decision-making in a time of economic crisis will involve emotions (Kevin, 2015).

Types of Decision Making

Decision making is categorized into four parts as suggested by Peretomode (2014), they are: creative decision, generic decision, intermediate decision and appellate decision.

Creative Decision Making

This is a kind of decision that requires extra effort in solving the problem at hand. It is called creative because problem solving here surpasses established pattern in handling issues in the organization or school. The principal in this instance employs a different and sometimes a totally new pattern to tackle issue when it seems very challenging. It is referred to a unique approach or pattern in solving seeming difficult issues.

Generic Decision Making

Going by the name generic, is such kind of decision making that focuses on the origin of an issue or issues before decisions are taken on them. Such decision making style bases so much concern on schools policies, principles, procedures, rules and regulations as it concern students and teacher. Reference is made always to high principle officers of the organization or school for them to take decision on matters that orders on students and teachers. Most management are always in preparation to resolve issues that are tag generic. In this kind of decision making process, staff and students welfare and discipline are referred to the principal.

Intermediate Decision Making

This is a kind of decision making by the decision making body in the country or system. Such system may be the ministry of education by sending a message to the principal on what to do concerning issue affecting the school on the necessary steps to be taken. It is usually a decision from the superior officer to the subordinate within the same organization. Such decision can be in form of request that may not augur well for the principal and as well parents. Principals may not consider the grave effect it may have on students to parents because principals are under authority, so may have little or nothing to do in solving the problem.

Appellate Decision Making

This is another kind of decision making style. Unlike the intermediate decision making style where instructions and orders come from the superiors like those in the education board and ministries of education, here decision as well as instruction flows from the subordinates to the principal within the same organization. Generally, appellate decisions are made in response to cases referred to the principal by his subordinate.

Decision making owes its function to a wide range of issues. In cognizance to the points listed above, it may be based on the leadership style the school principal uses that may warrant certain decision making in the school system. Most commonly operational leadership in the school today is either of democratic or autocratic leadership styles. Democratic leaders consider a lot of factors before decision making especially as may be such that affects the school in its entirety. It is difficult for decision making to pull through in autocratic leadership atmosphere unlike the democratic atmosphere. Reason being that autocratic leaders do not consider factors that may affect the school system before such decisions are taking. This is what Suzy in Heinz, Mark and Harold (2012) called "The ten minutes decision making". Such decision making are decisions made in haste depending on the circumstance surrounding the leader. Decisions of this kind may cause eternal damage to the system, may have immediate consequences to the system especially in the issues that affect both teachers and students. This also brings us to the fact there exist programmed and non-programmed decision. Both kind of decision is dependent on the nature of the situation on ground. That is to say, that programmed decision is decision taken handle issues of a structured school or organization while non-programmed handles issue of unstructured schools or organization.

Statement of the Problem

Schools are organizational set up for principals, teachers and students to meet for knowledge transmission from the principals across to students through the teachers. Principals in recent past have failed in their roles in bringing the much needed changes due to lack of knowledge of what to do. This is based on the fact that they do not possess the required information and knowledge as administrators due to neglect by the government. This is a fact that most secondary schools seems not be up to standard in terms of output of students and teachers which have down played on the credibility of the principals.

The school system is progressive in nature and therefore calls for information necessary to match up to changes and adjustment that may occur along the line. It is the place of principals to introduce and implement the necessary information required. Capacity building skills are all about creativity, innovation and implementation on the part of the principals to be inculcated into the school activities. Such activities are possible with the right communication skill and decision making skill. Could it be that the absence of the skills mentioned above are the problem of principals' ineffectiveness. The absence of this becomes evident that capacity is lacking in the administrative duties of the principals. This can be traced to the fact that the old knowledge they acquired is still out playing in them. Skill translates to new ideas and product of added knowledge and constant development through these means such as; seminars, conferences, workshops, symposiums, training and retraining of both the principals and all involved. Principals' seem to lag behind in this regard as a way of improving their administrative roles in the schools to ensure changes. This seems to be the bane of challenge in most secondary schools in Abia State.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate principals communication and decision making skills for effective administration of principal in public secondary schools in Abia State. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to:

1. to ascertain communication skills in the achievement of objectives of secondary school principals in Abia State,
2. to examine ways decision making skills helps secondary schools principals in maintaining order in Abia State,

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study.

1. In what ways do communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objective in Abia State?
2. In what ways do decision skills help principals in maintaining order in secondary school in Abia State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study;

- H0₁.** There is no significant difference between the mean ratings score of male and female principals on how communication skills in the achievement of objectives in secondary schools in Abia State.
- H0₂.** There is no significant difference between the mean ratings score of experienced and less experienced principals on how decision making skills help in maintaining order in secondary schools in Abia State.

Theory

The theoretical framework upon which this study is based lies on the human capital theory. This theory is a modern extension of Adam Smith's wage differentials and was developed extensively by Becker in 1964 in his book titled "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with special reference to Education". This theory stresses the positive relationship between increased education acquisition and productivity, skills and wages. According to this theory, it suggest that education or training raises the productivity of workers by impacting useful knowledge and skills, hence raising workers' future income by increasing their life through earnings (Becker, 1964). It therefore calls for a continuous investment on education because it will not only result in the increase in pay but will also result in the human resources development of an employee or the educated. Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2010) opined that many of the developing nations have thus realized that the principal mechanism for

developing human knowledge is the education system. Thus, they invest huge sum of money on education not only as an attempt to impact knowledge and skills to individuals but also to impact values, ideas, attitudes and aspirations which may be in the nation's best developmental interest. Human capital theory arises out of any activity able to raise individual worker productivity and this has been one of the most influential economic theories of western education. This theory has proved beyond all reasonable doubt the reason why an individual is not satisfied with a particular level of educational attainment but rather strives to achieve more. One who becomes a graduate (first degree) holder would want to become a master; and as well acquire a doctorate. This theory therefore provided a justification for a large public expenditure on education in developing and developed nations.

METHODOLOGY

The design of this study was a descriptive survey design. The population was all the 204 public secondary schools in the 17 Local Government Areas in Abia State (Abia State Ministry of Education 2023). The study made use of 135 principals in these public secondary schools who served as respondents. The researcher used simple random sampling technique to select 5 local government areas (3 urban and 2 rural), from which a sample size of 135 principals was selected. Specifically, 100 males and 35 female principals were drawn from the population. This showed that 66% of the population was used in consonance with Taro Yamen's formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = Population size
 n = Sample size
 e = Level of significance

In this study, N = 204
 Confidence level (e) = 0.05

Hence

$$n = \frac{204}{1 + 204(0.05)^2} = \frac{204}{1.51} = 135.09933775 \cong 135$$

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled Principals Communication And Decision Making Skills For Effective Administration of Principal Questionnaire (CDMSEAPQ). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method. A reliability index (r) of 0.84 was established; meaning that the instrument was reliable. The data collected from the respondents was presented in tables, and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the two (2) research questions. z-test statistics was used to test the two (2) hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presentation of Data to Answer Research Questions

Research Question 1: *In what ways do communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objective in secondary schools in Abia State?*

Table 1: Weighted mean, standard deviation and rank order statistics of male and female principals on ways communication skills help principals in the achievement of objectives in secondary school in Abia State.

S/N		Male=90		Female=30		Weighted mean (x ₁ x ₂)	Rank	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
1	Builds synergy in the school system	3.70	1.80	3.35	1.48	3.53	2 nd	Agreed
2	Creates an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals	3.59	1.59	3.25	1.25	3.42	3 rd	Agreed
3	Creates mutual understanding in the school system	3.83	1.39	3.25	1.25	3.54	1 st	Agreed
4	Information is broken down to the level of everyone to achieve target goals	3.66	1.55	3.02	1.40	3.34	4 th	Disagreed
5	Everyone is carried along in the school system	3.50	1.76	3.05	1.40	3.28	5 th	Agreed
6.	Hinders confidence among teachers in service delivery	3.03	1.68	1.78	1.45	2.41	6 th	Disagreed
		21.31	9.77	17.70	8.23	19.52		
		3.55	1.63	2.95	1.37	3.25		

Table 1 revealed that items in the rank order of 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th with serial numbers 3, 1, 2, 4 and 5 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were therefore agreed by the respondents on ways communication skills affect achievement of objectives of principals’ in secondary schools in Abia State while item which ranked 6th with serial number 6 has mean value below the criterion mean value of 2.50 and was disagreed by the respondents on ways communication skills affect achievement of objectives of principals in secondary schools in Abia State. Creating mutual understanding in the school system, building synergy in the school system, creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals, breaking of information to the level of everyone in order to achieve target and carrying everyone along in the school system on ways communication skills affect achievement of objectives of principals.

Research Question 2: *In what ways do decision skills help secondary school principals maintaining order secondary schools in Abia State?*

Table 2: Weighted mean, standard deviation and rank order statistics of experienced and less experienced principals on ways decision making skills help in maintaining order in secondary schools in Abia State.

S/N		Experienced 85		Less Experienced 35		Weighted mean (x_1x_2)	Rank	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
7	Goals are achieved within a short period of time	3.84	1.37	3.46	1.49	3.65	2 nd	Agreed
8	Creates direction for the school system	3.89	1.26	2.63	1.20	3.26	5 th	Agreed
9	Creates target for the school	3.94	1.58	3.43	1.25	3.67	1 st	Agreed
10	Channels organizational strength	3.70	1.43	3.45	1.29	3.58	4 th	Agreed
11	Leads high level productivity	3.83	1.37	3.46	1.49	3.65	2 nd	Agreed
		19.20	7.01	16.43	6.72	17.81		
		3.84	1.40	3.29	1.34	3.56		

Table 2 revealed that items in the rank order of 1st, 2nd, 2nd, 4th and 5th with serial numbers 9, 7, 11, 10 and 8 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were agreed by the principals on ways decision making skills affect maintenance of order by the principals in secondary schools in Abia State. This implies that the following are the ways decision making skills affect maintenance of order by the principals in secondary schools in Abia State by helping create targets in the school, achieving goals within a short period of time, leading to high level productivity, helping to channel organizational strength and helping create direction for the school system.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female principals on ways communication skills help secondary schools principals in the achievement of objectives in Abia State.

Table 4.6: z-test scores of the mean rating score of male and female principals on ways communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objectives in Abia State.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	90	3.55	1.63	118	1.98	1.96	significant
Female	30	2.95	1.37				

Table 3 revealed that male principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.55 and 1.63 while female principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.95 and 1.37 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 118 at an alpha significant level of 0.05; the calculated z-value of 1.98 is greater than the critical z-value of 1.96. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is a significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female principals on how communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objectives in Abia State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean rating score of experienced and less experienced principals on ways decision making skills help principals in maintaining of order in secondary schools in Abia State.

Table 4.7: z-test scores of the mean rating score of experienced and less experienced principals on ways decision making skills help principals in maintaining of order in secondary schools in Abia State.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Experienced	85	3.84	1.40	118	2.02	1.96	Significant
Less Experienced	35	3.29	1.34				

Table 4 revealed that experienced principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.84 and 1.40 while less experienced principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.29 and 1.34 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 118 at an alpha significant level of 0.05; the calculated z-value of 2.02 is greater than the critical z-value of 1.96. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the mean rating score of experienced and less experienced principals on how decision making skills help principals in maintaining order in secondary schools in Abia State.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data presented and analyzed above, the findings of this study were summarized as follows;

1. It was revealed that building synergy in the school system, creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals, creating mutual understanding in the school system, breaking down of information to the level of everyone to achieve target goals and carrying everyone along in the school system on ways communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objective in Abia State.
2. Ways decision making skills help principals in maintaining order in secondary school in Abia State include: achieving goals within a short period of time, creating direction for the school system, creating target for the school, channeling organizational strength and leading a high level productivity.
3. There is a significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female principals on ways communication skills help secondary school principals in the achievement of objective in Abia State.
4. There is a significant difference between the mean rating score of experienced and less experienced principals on ways decision making skills help principals in maintaining order in secondary school in Abia State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study were discussed under the following subheadings.

How Communication Skills Help Secondary School Principals in the Achievement of Objectives.

The findings of the study showed that building synergy in the school system, creating mutual understanding in school system, carrying everyone along in the school system, creating enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals have been agreed to by the respondents. Bennis and Nanus in Virginia (2008) emphasized that leadership is all about communicating and effective principals regularly utilize communication skills in soliciting beliefs and ideas, advocating positions, and persuading others. Hence, the tested hypothesis for this finding showed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on communication skill in achievement of objectives.

Ways Decision Making Skills Help Principals in Maintaining Order in Secondary Schools.

The findings of the study showed thus: goals are achieved within a short period of time, create direction for the school system, creates target for the school, channels organizational strength and leads to high level of productivity all agreed to and rated decision making skill as an aided way of

maintaining order. In line with the findings, Fatima (2012) posited that decision making process involves areas related to the students' wellbeing, teaching and non-teaching, Parent Teacher Associations and is concerned with the following responsibilities on the school principal;

- a. the principal must identify his staff members as a team working for the growth and development of the students;
- b. the principal must realize that as a team each member, staff and students have a large part to play in decisions that determine the school rules, regulations and programmes. School administration through staff meetings, student's representatives, clubs, committees and organizations should be involved in the running of the school through proper delegation of activities and responsibilities.
- c. the school principal must ensure that decisions and procedures in the school must be consistent with the underlying philosophy and mission of the school. This means that decisions should at all times aimed at achieving the set goal, objectives and interest of the school.
- d. the principal together with members of staff must always keep the ministry of education, school board and general public fully informed of the school policies, programmes, failures and successes.

The tested hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference for experienced and less experienced principals on ways decision making skills help in maintaining order.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the research, the researcher concluded that communication skills and decision making skills help secondary schools principals in Abia State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Principals should ensure that all forms of communication skills ranging from verbal to written to gestures and their likes be adopted and practiced in schools in for the achievement of objectives particularly when addressing teachers, students and all other educational stakeholders within the school.
2. Decision making skills of principals should be such that seeks the opinion of other members of the school when making crucial decisions concerning issues that affect the school.

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